

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX FORMATION BETWEEN MOLYBDIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID. PART I. POLARIMETRIC STUDIES

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The complex formation between tartaric and molybdic acids in solution has been studied polarimetrically. The reaction is shown to be governed by an equilibrium of the type $H_2MoO_4 + H_2T \xrightleftharpoons{K} H_2(MoO_4 T, H_2O)$ and the equilibrium constant $K (= 1.03 \times 10^2)$

has been calculated. The reaction goes to completion when the concentration of one of the components is 4 times the other. The possible causes for exalted rotation and other peculiarities have been discussed and a probable constitution of the complex compound is given in keeping with the co-ordination theory of valency.

The peculiarities of optical rotatory powers and rotatory dispersions of tartaric acid and its derivatives have attracted considerable attention ever since they were first discovered by Biot. Garnier (*Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 785; 105, 85; 1889, 108, 942) investigated the changes in rotatory power of solutions of tartaric acid in presence of alkali molybdates of varying concentrations and obtained maximum rotations when the acid and the salt were in equimolecular proportions and suggested the formation of definite complex. Rosenheim and Itzig (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 707) considered the complex as containing one molecule of sodium tartrate and varying amounts of molybdic oxide, viz. 1,2,2,4,4, etc. Itzig (*ibid.*, 1901, 34, 1372) added varying amounts of either sodium molybdate or ammonium paramolybdate to the solution of hydrogen tartrate and came to the same conclusion. Klason and Köhler (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3946) extended Itzig's work and found that the maximum rotation given by sodium hydrogen tartrate depends on other factors besides the amount of alkali metal such as the proportion of molybdic acid, the concentration of the active substance and the temperature of the solution. The work was subsequently taken up by many, notably Mazzucchalli (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1910, 19, ii, 439; *Gazzetta*, 1913, 43, ii, 26), Grossman (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1606; 1905, 38, 3874; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 41, 43; 1908, 60, 50), Rimbach (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 53, 397; 1922, 100, 393), Darmois (*Compt. rend.*, 1923, 176, 1140; 1924, 179, 629; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1928, 43, 1214), Britton and Jackson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1055), Yeu ki Heng (*J. chim. phys.*, 1936, 33, 383) and Delsal (*J. chim. phys.*, 1938, 35, 350).

The conclusions reached by these authors are conflicting and sometimes questionable excepting the indications of the formation of a definite complex. As regards the molecular proportion of the two components in the complex, some workers have assumed the ratio to be one and some, more than one,

dependent on the proportion in which they are present in the mixture. The difficulty to decide the problem is the continuous failure to get the compound in a well-crystallised solid state of fixed composition. Although in a very few cases crystallisation was tried, the composition of the product was found to vary. Compounds of the general formula $R_2(XO_3)_2C_4H_4O_8$ [R=alkali metal, X=Mo] have been prepared by Rosenheim and Itzig (*loc. cit.*) in crystalline form; on the other hand Handerson and Barr (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896 69, 1455) prepared a series of salts of the composition $XO_3(Na C_4H_4O_8)_n$.

Most of the previous studies suffer from the defect that two or more variables, which have a pronounced influence on optical rotation, have been superimposed upon one another. The presence of alkali metals or NH_4^+ ions, either as a salt of any of the two component acids or as a free base, may change the rotation value considerably; the pH of the system also is a very important factor in this connection. Moreover, studies on the optical rotation were confined to one wave-length only, but it is known that complex compounds behave anomalously toward light; in one wave-length it may seem inactive, while for shorter or longer wave-lengths it may show activity in different directions. Therefore, it is risky to draw any conclusion from studies of rotations at one particular wave-length.

The object of the present investigation is to study in detail, the peculiarities of optical rotations manifested on the addition of *d*-tartaric acid to a molybdic acid sol avoiding the above mentioned shortcomings, to determine the reaction and the composition of the reaction product that is formed. The optical rotations were measured at four different wave-lengths.

EXPERIMENTAL

The optical rotations were measured in a triple field polarimeter which gave the values with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The wave-lengths selected were $690 \mu\mu$, $578 \mu\mu$, $546 \mu\mu$ and $436 \mu\mu$. The wave-length $690 \mu\mu$ was taken out from an ordinary electric lamp with the help of a suitable filter and for the other three, mercury arc lamp was used from which the respective wave-lengths were isolated with suitable filters. Molybdic acid (MoO_3) was used in colloid form, carefully purified by dialysis, *d*-tartaric acid (H.T) (B.D.H. product) was further purified by recrystallisation. Redistilled water was always used for making solutions.

In Table I are shown the values for optical rotation obtained by adding increasing amounts of MoO_3 to a definite quantity of tartaric acid and the reverse of that, is followed and noted in Table II. The length of the polarimeter tube was always 0.54 dm, and the temperature was 25° ,

The change in the nature of rotatory dispersion of pure tartaric acid solution, brought about by the addition of molybdc acid, is represented graphically in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Rotatory dispersion of tartaric acid & complex molybdo-tartaric acid.

TABLE I
Conc. of $H_2T = 5.27 \times 10^{-3} M$

Ratio MoO_3 H_2T	690 μ .	578 μ .	546 μ .	436 μ .
1 0.25	+0.04	+0.05	+0.05	+0.08
2 0.50	+0.05	+0.06	+0.07	+0.14
3 0.75	+0.07	+0.09	+0.11	+0.21
4 1.00	+0.08	+0.10	+0.12	+0.22
5 2.00	+0.11	+0.14	+0.15	+0.29
6 3.00	+0.11	+0.14	+0.17	+0.32
7 4.00	+0.12	+0.15	+0.17	+0.33
8 5.00	+0.12	+0.15	+0.17	+0.33
9 6.00	+0.12	+0.15	+0.17	+0.33

TABLE II
 Conc. of $\text{MoO}_3 = 2.53 \times 10^{-2} M$

Ratio $\text{H}_2\text{T}/\text{MoO}_3$	Rotation at wave-lengths (obs.)			
	690 $\mu\mu$.	578 $\mu\mu$.	546 $\mu\mu$.	436 $\mu\mu$.
a. 0.25	+0.12	+0.19	+0.21	+0.41
b. 0.50	+0.25	+0.35	+0.38	+0.80
c. 0.75	+0.35	+0.48	+0.52	+1.01
d. 1.00	+0.46	+0.58	+0.62	+1.18
e. 2.00	+0.63	+0.77	+0.85	+1.69
f. 3.00	+0.69	+0.89	+0.99	+1.83
g. 4.00	+0.80	+0.98	+1.10	+2.02
h. 5.00	+0.84	+1.02	+1.15	+2.08
i. 6.00	+0.86	+1.07	+1.19	+2.12

It will be noticed in Table I that increased addition of MoO_3 increases the rotation gradually in all the wave-lengths terminating with a constant maximum, when the concentration of MoO_3 is about 4 times that of H_2T , and it seems that MoO_3 does not go into reaction any more after that. Referring to Table II, it is found that the rotation increases as before and after the value 4 is reached for the ratio $\text{H}_2\text{T}/\text{MoO}_3$, the values increase slowly, probably due to H_2T remaining completely unreacted. In the later part of Table II if the rotation values given by H_2T , when present separately at the same concentration as in the respective mixtures, be subtracted from the observed values of the mixtures, the resulting figures should remain constant from the stages where the extra amount of H_2T added would remain completely uncombined. The results of such subtractions are given in Table III, and it will be seen that the rotation becomes steady after the value for the ratio $\text{H}_2\text{T}/\text{MoO}_3$ is 4.

TABLE III
 Optical rotation at different wave-lengths.

	690 $\mu\mu$.			578 $\mu\mu$.			546 $\mu\mu$.			436 $\mu\mu$.		
	Obs.	Due to H_2T	Diff.									
(f)	+0.69	+0.07	+0.62	+0.89	+0.08	+0.81	+0.99	+0.11	+0.88	+1.83	+0.13	+1.70
(g)	+0.80	+0.10	+0.70	+0.98	+0.11	+0.87	+1.10	+0.13	+0.97	+2.02	+0.16	+1.86
(h)	+0.84	+0.12	+0.72	+1.02	+0.15	+0.87	+1.15	+0.16	+0.99	+2.08	+0.20	+1.88
(i)	+0.86	+0.15	+0.71	+1.07	+0.19	+0.88	+1.19	+0.20	+0.99	+2.12	+0.25	+1.87

The increase of rotation with the increase in the concentration of MoO_3 has been assumed by several workers to be due to the formation of new

compounds of composition varying from $\text{Na}_2(\text{MoO}_3)_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8$ to $\text{Na}_2(\text{MoO}_3)_4\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8$; Britton and Jackson (*loc. cit.*) suggested the probable equilibrium reaction of the type

There is no justification for assuming a new compound each time the rotation value changes. On the other hand from our observations in Tables I and II, we are led to believe that the reaction between the two acids is governed by an equilibrium of the type

The observed facts can be easily explained on the formation of this complex acid which has much higher molecular rotatory power than pure H_2T . The increase of the concentration of either of the components will help the formation of the complex more and more showing increased rotation and the reaction becomes complete when the concentration of either of the components is about 4 times the other, indicated by the steady rotation value observed after that stage.

Assuming equimolecular combination and the applicability of the law of mass action,

$$K = \frac{[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_3\text{T}, \text{H}_2\text{O})]}{[\text{H}_2\text{T}][\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4]} = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{T}]_{\text{free}} [\text{MoO}_3]_{\text{free}}} \quad \dots \text{ (i)}$$

Observed rotation of any mixture = (molecular rotation of the complex) $\times$

$$[\text{complex}] + (\text{molecular rotation of free } \text{H}_2\text{T}) \times (\text{H}_2\text{T})_{\text{free}} \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

For mixtures giving maximum rotations, $[\text{complex}] = [\text{H}_2\text{T}]$, when MoO_3 is in excess.

$$\text{Then observed max. rotation} = (\text{mol. rotation of complex}) \times [\text{H}_2\text{T}]$$

$$\therefore \text{Molecular rotation of the complex} = \frac{\text{Obs. max. rotation}}{[\text{H}_2\text{T}]} \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

$$\text{Similarly, mol. rotation of free } \text{H}_2\text{T} = \frac{\text{Obs. rotation of free } \text{H}_2\text{T}}{[\text{H}_2\text{T}]} \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

and in any intermediate mixture, the concentration of free H_2T is given by

$$[\text{H}_2\text{T}]_{\text{free}} = \text{Total conc. of } \text{H}_2\text{T} - [\text{complex}] \quad \dots \text{ (v)}$$

Applying the above 5 equations to the data in Table I, the equilibrium constant K has been calculated as shown in Table IV below.

TABLE IV

Molecular rotations (for 0.54 dm. tube)	Wave-lengths			
	690 μ .	578 μ .	546 μ .	436 μ .
Complex acid	22.8	28.4	32.2	62.6
H_2T (free) (calc. from actual rotation measurements)	1.01	1.15	1.24	1.52

TABLE IV—(contd.)

Solution Number in Table I.	Equilibrium constant $K \times 10^3$			
2	1.08	0.86	0.90	1.26
4	0.82	0.86	1.15	1.00
5	1.13	1.46	0.89	0.98
	Mean $K = 1.03 \times 10^3$			

It is found that the values of K obtained, are fairly constant supporting the validity of our assumptions. Now, from the known values of K and concentrations of both H_2T and MoO_3 , the concentration of the complex acid and free H_2T in any mixture can be calculated and hence the rotation value to be observed in such solutions can be precalculated from equation (ii) mentioned above. In Table V we have compared the rotation value thus calculated with that actually observed to test further the truth of our assumptions made before.

TABLE V

Conc. of $H_2T \times 10^2$.	Conc. of $MoO_3 \times 10^2$.	Rotations ($\mu\mu$) at							
		690 $\mu\mu$.		578 $\mu\mu$.		546 $\mu\mu$.		436 $\mu\mu$.	
		Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
7.635M	3.832	+0.75	+0.08	+0.95	+1.10	+1.1	+1.1	+1.20	+1.21
"	10.89	+1.45	+1.15	+1.18	+1.16	+2.05	+2.21	+4.40	+4.42
7.29	4.39	+0.09	+0.08	+1.11	+1.10	+1.12	+1.12	+2.35	+2.22
"	17.60	+1.16	+1.16	+1.20	+1.19	+2.225	+2.22	+4.44	+4.43
5.907	23.63	+1.13	+1.12	+1.16	+1.15	+1.18	+1.17	+3.35	+3.33
23.63	"	+1.45	+1.43	+1.56	+1.54	+1.63	+1.62	+1.23	+1.26
9.437	18.06	+1.19	+1.18	+1.24	+1.22	+2.27	+2.25	+5.3	+5.50
20.31	"	+1.40	+1.38	+1.49	+1.47	+1.55	+1.53	+1.06	+1.07
76.12	25.37	+1.62	+1.60	+1.77	+1.74	+1.87	+1.83	+1.64	+1.60

It will be noticed that the calculated and observed values are of the same order.

DISCUSSION

The reaction between molybdic and tartaric acids is a molecular one, one molecule of each combining together. We were at first led to think like that seeing the analogous rotatory power effected by the compound from the antimonius acid and tartaric acids, in which the complex compound is isolable and the emetic (potassium antimonyl tartrate) includes the two acids in the proportion 1:1. Our assumption is also amply justified by the observations made above (Tables IV and V).

The change in the nature of the rotatory dispersion curve and large exaltation of optical rotations of H_2T , brought about by the addition of MoO_3 , is due to a complex compound formation governed by an equilibrium reaction. But the nature of the combination is not revealed from such empirical representations, and we have discussed below this aspect of the reaction.

The cause of enhanced rotation may be explained in two ways, viz., (1) the reaction between the two acids takes place in such a way that a new centre of dissymmetry is formed or (2) the H_2T consists of two labile forms of oppositely rotatory dynamic isomers, one form of which preferentially reacts with the complete suppression of the other.

Now according to hypothesis (1) the union between the two acids may take place, thus :

Molybdenum shows variable valency and it can easily take up electrons ; here the combination has taken place with a semi-polar bond and a new centre of dissymmetry is formed round the positively charged oxygen atom. The latent optical activity, associated with the oxygen atom, is thereby developed to show enhanced activity. Support is given to this hypothesis by the structurally similar compounds of Phillips and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2352 ; 1926, 2079 ; 1927, 188 ; 1928, 3000) who

have assigned the structure $\begin{array}{c} R' \\ \diagup \\ S^+ \\ \diagdown \\ R \end{array} \rightarrow O^-$ to the sulphoxides which have

comparable rotatory power. Burgess and Hunter (*ibid.*, 1929, 2838) accounted for the behaviour of borotartaric acid on a similar hypothesis. But in a number of cases this is untenable. It fails to explain why many other hydroxyl compounds are without any influence and also stand against the general tendency of the organic hydroxy-acids to form closed chain compounds.

Much more probable is the other hypothesis (2) where the existing equilibrium condition of the two dynamic isomers of tartaric acid is assumed to be disturbed by the presence of MoO_3 , the latter being capable of combining with one of the isomers only. In that case the second isomer is gradually transformed into the reactive form to maintain the equilibrium condition. Thus, in certain circumstances the whole of H_2T in the solution may combine with MoO_3 to give rise to simple rotatory dispersion. The anomalous rotation of H_2T itself has been explained on the hypothesis (Lowry and Austin, *Phil. Trans.*, 1922, A, 222, 249 ; Bancroft and Davis, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 897) that the observed rotatory power of H_2T is due to the difference of two much larger and nearly equal rotation values of two labile isomers in H_2T , and these are responsible for the small variation of optical rotation against wave-length. Lucas and Schowb (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1932, 5, 52) came to the same conclusion from spectrographic studies of H_2T .

On the Bohr theory of atomic structure, molybdenum ($1s^2 2s^2 2p^6 3s^2 3p^4 3d^1 4s^2 4p^4 4d^5 5s$) like Cr, Fe, Ni and Pt, etc., which form well-defined compound of co-ordination number 6, is a member of one of the group of elements, the planetary electrons of which are undergoing reorganisation to show variable valency and marked colour in its compounds. Co-ordination number 8 also is exhibited in compound of the type $R_2[Mo(CN)_6]^{IV}$, and marked stability associated with the complex ion $[Mo(CN)_6]^{IV}$, is due to the fact that the cyanide units are regularly distributed round the central atom with effective atomic number 54, the same as that of Xenon. But the molybdotartrate compound is not so stable and is susceptible to easy reduction and so in all probability the complex compound is formed of an incomplete shell with co-ordination number 6, as shown below.

The X-ray analysis of $Ag_2[MoO_4]$ by Wyckoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1994) has disclosed oxygen atoms are tetrahedrally distributed round the central Mo atom and accordingly we can represent molybdic

acid as $H \left[\begin{array}{c} O \\ | \\ O - Mo - O \\ | \\ O \end{array} \right] H$ and co-ordination with H_2T occurs forming a compound as,

a five membered ring compound is formed with a molecule of H_2O within the co-ordination sphere. The corresponding oxalate compound crystallised as pyridine salt by Spittle and Wardlaw (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1867) and Rosenheim (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 11, 225) was found by analysis to have a composition $RH[MoO_3, C_2O_4, H_2O]$.

My grateful thanks are due to Sir J. C. Ghosh for his kind interest and helpful criticisms in this work.